
Is Jordan an appropriate chance to enhance the success opportunities of the Taiwan investment when adopting the partnership?

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ABSTRACT

This paper searched for the range of appropriateness of Jordan as a suitable chance to enhancing the Taiwan economic investment opportunities, when adopting the basis of partnership instead of cooperation in the light of suffering the most countries from current economic depression which is resulting from different economic crisis, made some countries to search for the new economic strategies and concepts considering as solutions in different international strategic environments, on condition of they are characterized with its capacity to achieve the equality and fairness doctrine between the partner countries. Taiwan is the most important advanced entity in both economic and administrative areas locally and internationally, but it is facing the political pressures because of the circumstance with China, in addition to the negative economic reactions resulting from the regional competition with Asia developing countries. Adopting the strategy of partnership in founding the companies in the friendly and allied nations instead of adopting the current used approach of cooperation, it makes hopes to develop the opportunities of investment outside, and it processes and reduces some of the restrainers and more by implementing the concept of globalization. Achieving any strategy and applicable new concept requires making the extensive studies, introducing the integrated strong plans, and choosing the most viable environment which contributes to accept and support the idea. Jordan is particularly one of the hopeful countries in economy, it seeks to achieve its objectives, coping with the development and advancement, and it has a strong relation with Taiwan. The question arises and needs the answer: Is Jordan considered as an opportunity to enhance the

opportunities of increasing the investment of Taiwan when adopting the basis of partnership?

Keywords: Partnership, Cooperation, Dominancy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Taiwan emphasized its capacities and abilities in coping with the world. It introduces itself positively, because it has made achievements by its name and it attracted the entire world [1]. Although the economic relationship between Taiwan and China doesn't deny the range of China dependence [2], on Taiwan economy power internationally in different areas such as technology which is unlimited, and it is featured with communication sector when it reached, in some products, to the first levels at all the world. The creativity in Taiwan came as a result of a strong planning on perfect bases. Knowledge and science are the source of power to each aspect whether small or big, they are able to operate the capacities, use the opportunities and achieve its objectives more than others. The big size of commercial exchange with China put heavy shades on the main components of Taiwan which emphasizes itself independently [3]. But Taiwan economy is mainly depending on the commercial exchange with China, this way threatens its identity directly [4] in view of the difference of the dependence way for both, Taiwan depends on small and medium enterprises, whereas China depends on big enterprises which are supported by country. Taiwan wants to increase its capacity in the area of independency, making its economy independent to decrease the ability of China to contain the Taiwan economy. The relationship between Jordan and Taiwan is historic [5]; it may use to build a vastest and biggest economic cooperation between both countries [6] to get rid of the problems resulting from the regional competition, it may use to build a vastest

and biggest economic cooperation between both countries to get rid of the problems resulting from the regional competition, reducing from the dependency on the Chinese economy, settling the shortage of labor [7], and changing the short term policies. Taiwan is featured with different areas which are able to use as an independent economic power without depending on China and leaving the regional competition. It is characterized by quality and rareness and there is no similar in other countries even China. Such as it has a strong educational system [8], enabling it to help and give advice to all countries in particular Jordan to solve the educational problems relating to education there, also in the field of environment and the characterized service sector which is introduced in Taiwan anywhere and helps largely decreasing the administrative corruption and the social defects in other countries like Jordan [9]. The Taiwan leading experience in supporting the tourism sector dealing as a science making its experiment as certified to be a source in the field of tourism. Building a standing relationship on implementing a new concept instead of the traditional concepts, it may carry out the solutions for both parties such as depending on the strategic partnership instead of cooperation being more able to achieve its intended objectives in better way on condition of implementing them in stages and providing the details.

2. METHODOLOGY

Variety and difference in the available options are the most important priorities for the corporate countries, because they provide the flexibility in response and calling the different strategic environment conditions, this can be expressed through the concept of not putting the eggs in one basket [10], making the experiments of modern concepts generate a mature thinking especially in the economic and politic conditions which are unstable and resulting from international and regional interferences of some greater countries that want to direct the policies as requires by its interests [11]. Most of people try to find solutions and clarifications of the situation of the Chinese Taiwan relationship and what they are surrounded with attraction processes [12]. Such as there is an available possibility of economic convergence between them, but there is a lack of possibility of political convergence. This matter requires finding applicable logical solutions through leaving the context according to different equations abstaining the previous used traditional solutions, because they provide the best results, for example, replacing the concept of cooperation in the economic

relations between countries with other concept that is more useful as the strategic partnership is considered as a logical solution leading to the best results. It achieves more mutual benefits for both parties of equation. Searching for the appropriate strategic partner under the political condition of Taiwan is not easy, because it is influenced by the China clear interferences, but it is not possible due to that Taiwan is connected with distinctive relations throughout history with many friendly nations. For example, the Jordanian – Taiwan relation contained more than one type of strong cooperation [13]. The most important aspect in Jordan is that Jordan is one of the most Middle East countries that have security and safety, and it has several elements such as it has the international relations net with all countries around world especially the greatest countries [14], but the most important aspect is the Jordan will to develop and progress its community and people [15], it encourages the investment, and goes along with the corporate business. Adopting the concept of partnership requires a perfect integrated implementation based on extensive studies that answer many questions and exceed the surrounded conditions [16], for example the lack of Taiwan labor shall be filled, and it provides the solutions for the high ranges of unemployment in Jordan [17]. In addition to other examples. Also, adopting the idea of partnership requires hardworking by both to succeeding this concept by depending the method of stages, clarifying the requirements of both before implementing because this gives the power and the solidity of implementing and adopting this concept. Hence, the modernity of transfer between both concepts which are partnership and cooperation shows the importance of answering the question which is: Is Jordan an appropriate opportunity to enhance the success opportunities of the Taiwan investment when adopting the partnership? To cover all aspects of matter in details, the search will be made under the following titles: Advantages of Taiwan economy, the commercial exchange between China and Taiwan, challenges of Taiwan economy, elements of Jordan economy, the needs of Jordan local market, Jordan-Taiwan relations, the concept of strategic partnership with its general benefits, benefits of the strategic partnership for Taiwan and Jordan, elements of the strategic partnership.

2.1 Advantages of Taiwan Economy

Taiwan is characterized by a high level of development; it is one of the most important modern democratic entity which is based on the equality and justice between its citizens [18]. This matter is

reflecting on the economic competency of Taiwan citizens by the inventions in the industrial and commercial fields at all levels. These earnings is not a result of chance, but there are many factors which contributed in emerging these capacities and abilities such as: First, capacity and determination, although the small size of the geographic country, it achieved many objectives and made competitions internationally, it exceeds many of European and Asian countries, for example, Taiwan reached the first rank in exporting mushroom and lemon in the international market in 1993. Second, the quality excellence, Taiwan is characterized by quality through making the quality products which have an acceptance in the international markets. In 1993, it has a biggest computer producing stations and electronic devices [19]. Which are based on the distinctive technological capacities, in addition to produce what the market needs. Accordingly, there is an urgent need to Taiwan products which are desired by most of countries, this is emphasized by Taiwan capacity on providing 77% of the world exports of the scanners, Laptops (personal computer), and it occupied the first place in producing the bicycles which were 95% of the world market. Third, the political openness, Taiwan directed to democracy and against oppression [20] by filing the Martial laws which lasted 38 years, and making the first democratic Presidential elections in 1996, implementing the consecutive reforms, depending the open society method, all of that increases the mutual confidence between Taiwan and the international political parties which make Taiwan characterized by a high level of confidence with other countries. Fourth, depending the modern scientific methods of development [21]. Fifth, acquiring the different experiments of the war needs of the heavy and light of the defense industries to be operated in the future industry [22]. Sixth, making job vacancies and taking the advantage from the available vacancies when Taiwan enabled to read the international global statement and its needs by other invites to depending on the developing new methods, for example, the concept of free trade and free market [23].

2.2 Commercial Exchange between China and Taiwan

A- The different conflicts, whether it was political or military between China and Taiwan, have influenced on the commercial between both parties. These conflicts lasted for thirty years in the duration between 1949 until 1979. China especially after its interior reforms in 1978, it ordered to open the

connections of commerce, mail and transportation with Taiwan[24], the China's interest appeared when it tried to buy the Taiwan products through Hong Kong with a cost of 460 million \$ in 1981. but China's intention didn't stop there, on the hope of encouraging the trade between two countries by declaring the decree of the commercial exchange between both countries without subjecting the Taiwan goods to the fees tax for one year. But Taiwan didn't respond the Chinese initial till 1985, Taiwan ordered the dependence on the basis of "not interfering in the exports undirected to the mainland. The commercial Exchange between the two countries lasted for 20 years until reached 112 exchanges in two decades. The level of trade reached 134 in 1981 which started with 460 million \$ and reached 37.4 billion \$ in 2002 [25]. China had the third in the commercial partnership with Taiwan in 1993 after USA and Japan [26]. Whereas the exports, China became the biggest market for exports to Taiwan in the same year. In 2002, China became the biggest market for exports to Taiwan; numbers show the importance of the commercial exchange between both parties. The commercial agreement between China and Taiwan is inevitable for the both, and they signed many agreements between them. In 2013 they signed a commercial agreement Cross-strait in services (CASSTA) [27]. Although the trading with the external world is important, but Taiwan is worry about the results of Free Trade Agreement reinforce china intentions to be united with Taiwan, and this is will effect on the formation principles of the State in Taiwan. The Framework Agreement on Economic Cooperation between China and Taiwan is one of the most important agreements signed between them because China will reduce customs fees on 539 large-scale products in exchange for Taiwan to reduce customs fees on 237 Chinese products [28], some opponents believe that the agreement represents a step toward further domination of China because the Taiwan economy will rely more on China.

2.3 Taiwanese economy Challenges

Taiwan's economy suffers from many challenges and difficulties on the economic level as well as the

political side with China, but the most important challenges are the following:

- A- Regional competition. The rush of the world countries toward China oblige Taiwan now to seriously consider the need to search on ways to maintain uniqueness in its industry in the first place, despite the appearance of many competitors at the regional level [29], Especially in the perfect Taiwan industries such as Information Technology Industry is produced in Vietnam in lower cost because cheap labor.
- B- The dependence on the Chinese economy. The world depends mainly on china currently, which requires increased production of China's economy significantly and therefore its negative impact on Taiwan's economy to a large extent. This is not threatening economic side but also it increases China's ability to contain and reunified Taiwan. Taiwan has been affected by the United Nations decision and its recognition, for example, despite a serious desire to join the Asian Investment Bank in infrastructure but it has not China's approval until now [30], this limits the ambition of Taiwan to participate in many different experiences in the future.
- C- Lack of labor. the Taiwanese government suffers from lack of labor, where the ministry of Taiwanese labor confirmed lately in July 2015 the urgent need for stop of continuing lack at Labor force which decreased by 180,000 jobs in that year [31], Taiwan seeks to providing alternatives to be able to reinforcement the economy and get rid of the negative effects of the phenomenon.
- D- Short term policies. The government issued some of special decisions after global crisis 2008/2009; the short term policies and keeping away from realistic thinking or stability in the long-term planning such as protection of young worker's policy as an incentive for work owners to provide young workers in minimum salaries.
- E- Military readiness situation: Statues of permanent Military readiness is considered cumbersome especially for the state budget because it represents an excessive pressure on the state budget, as a result of the political sector with China still not solved, so it will be a spectacle in front of the military expensive. The understanding to

solve any difficult problems between the two countries represents an important objective, so if it achieves it will help to stop wasting the energies and to reduce the negative role of collapse the competition between the Great current powers (USA and China).

- F- the bad employment for the human resources: the exploitation of the human resources is something important in any country, so the countries which exploited these human resources can avoid all the problems that faced it, especially when the result from the education is in line with the requirements and the needs of the labor force which are represented of the stability and it can exploit it positively. In this case, the state has to reinforce the efforts , improve the performance , service and the human resources' incomes; for example : the number of the labors from the labor force in the financial sector in Taiwan is about double the used labor number in USA , and that indicates the effect of the apparent imbalance [32].
- G- Do not exploit the unique features: the unique features in Taiwan community are various, and the Creative thinking is reflected by the availability of the political democracy system freedom in Taiwan which confesses of their rights in Self-realization. The result of excellence in production, especially in Information and Communication Technology field and the electronic materials represents the best proof of that. It seems that there is a question: what is the role of state that should play it to present its abilities? for instance: Taiwan characterized in an excellence level in education, medicine, etc. in addition to that there are a huge number of available human resources which can be exploited and used positively so It is possible to be of great benefit to the state.

2.4 Jordan's economic fundamentals

In the early 1950s; Jordan- which is described as one of the emerging countries- emphasis a continuous improvement in the economy. Although, Jordan is suffering from raring of the natural resources, but it began to make a series of economic reforms after the financial crisis in 1988 to treat the Financial imbalance and to correct the Structural economical distortions to achieve the economic stability at that

time [33]. Despite the positive made efforts but the high rates of unemployment and poverty are not treat. Since King Abdullah the second took throne; the Jordanian governments concentrated on the development of the Economic and political reforms, also concentrated on the importance to connect the two sectors public and privet to achieve the sustainable development [34]. In nutshell, this will lead to improve citizens' living standards and raise the level of the provided services. Jordan has been arrived to an advance level in development based on protection of the objectives that achieved earlier, and which also has been relied on it as a future development principle to complete the new requirements and to increase its ability to face the conditions and challenges which are happening in the strategic environment at various international, regional and local levels. but the situation in Jordan will continue to be a defining moment in the minds of observers to see what the advantages of the Jordanian economy are, which will make it able to stable in front of the current difficult facts on the global stage now [35]. Jordan at the regional and international levels is a safe haven for the Arab peoples, whether for tourism or stability, also is the largest country to receive refugees in the world from different countries and that happened for various reasons, starting from the Palestinian refugees' crises, Iraqi to the Syrian [36]. This thing increased the burden of the state to host these refugees because the rarely of the abilities and resources. Despite the difficulties and challenges that facing Jordan, but it has a strong base of international relations with various countries around the world as: USA, Russia, China, United Kingdom, France and other countries. Despite the small size of the country, it plays an important role in the international and regional arena. In addition to that, Jordan is one of the most important anti-terrorism stations that contribute to the maintenance of international peace and stability through the multiplicity of participation in international peacekeeping forces in various humanitarian missions [37].

2.5 Local Jordanian market needs

There is a lot of Local Jordanian market needs represent in: First: Technological industries, Jordan is one of the most technologically advanced countries, basically, it depends on the using of the Modern professions and the technological electricity machines, for instance: there are a large number of traffic lights, Security Cameras which used to the security and Protection Purposes [38]. In addition to that, the electronic boards which used in the main

components of the advices. Second, the electronic services: Although the advanced technological level that Jordan has been achieved but it still lake of the experience and trust to make the daily life easier for the citizen. For instance; Payment of bills and the financial commitments service through the smart cards is still weak, because it does not have the Professional qualified staff to provide the Domestic services especially in the matter of the entertainment system [39]. Third, Alternative Energy: because of Jordan suffering in lacking various kinds of petroleum products so this makes a significant contribution to determining the possibilities of the state and reducing the chances of success [40]. Fourth; recycling : recycling of the old materials and using it with a maximum efficiency is important also the recycling of the Scarce resources which used by the local citizen with limited income is important , in addition to use of these materials for humanitarian and global disasters as earthquakes , volcano and wars is important to recycle it especially in the countries that have humanitarian missions as the Syrian Refugees [41]; especially that Jordan has a number of experiences through the expanding of Jordanian participation in various international peacekeeping operations. Fifth; tourism industry: sometimes, all the Infrastructure and the environmental conditions do not help to provide the best services and the availability of means of transport as the availability of the fast and the comfortable Express train will help to arrive to the tourist areas quickly and comfortably [42]. Professionalism in the tourism industry is urgent because it achieves the best interest of the state. Sixth: improving of the Educational practical approaches and applications: the using of some old approaches and concepts and using other old methods contributes to make the output of the Learning process is weak; Jordan is looking forward to the educational curricula which enrich the student's abilities to provide the required scientific research at various grades to be an incentive in the future to achieve a distinguished scientific position.

2.6 Relationship between Jordan – Taiwan

For Taiwan, Jordan is an important country. During the History; in 1959, the relationships between them have been supported through the visiting of King Al-Hussein at that time and these relations are continuing until now. There is a big exchange of the trading between Jordan and Taiwan where the volume of trading is 300 Million Dollars., and much of the imports are from Taiwan and China, Taiwan imports from Jordan the Potash, Phosphate, minerals,

drugs, dead-sea Products and olive [43]. There is six Taiwanese Companies: five of them work in the Textile and one of them works in building a factory for Road lighting which is currently being established in Jordan [44]. In addition to that there is a student exchange to teach the Taiwanese the Arabic Language in the Jordanian Universities and at the same time to the Jordanian Students study in Taiwan at various Programs as PhD program, Master Program and some Strategic studies to exchange the experiences between the two parties [45].

2.7 Concept of strategic partnership and its advantages

Strategic partnership definition and its general benefits: The partnership defines as the external Incorporation which refers to achieve Maximum cooperation between the two parties, includes; productivity activity, or service or commercial works according to the corporation agreement between the partners as part of the permanent joint ownership [46]. Also the definition of strategic partnership includes the alliance [47] which the institute is still holds this description is Independent and is seeking to achieve its common objectives, advantages and hopes. The partnership definition is not limited only to one type of activities but it may be commercial, technological and financial [48]. All countries are seeking to achieve the economic integration which can be achieved through the strategic partnership. The strategic partnership has a lot of general benefits as: First: the availability of exchanging the acknowledgement and experiences between the partners. Second: there is a chance to achieve a financial Profits and a capital at the local level [49]. Third: Provide job opportunities that will increase the exports and decrease the imports. Fourth: decrease the difficulties and avoid the risks between the partners as a result of cooperation. Fifth: provide the protection and the necessary raw materials. Sixth: production with a low cost. Seventh: Adopting the principle of transparency in the relationships.

2.8 Strategic partnership benefits for Taiwan

There are a lot of benefits for the two parties, so that each one seeks to achieve objectives that will help the common interests for the two parties. The benefits for Taiwan are: First: to avoid the Regional Competition; with China, southern Korea, Hong Kong, Singapore and Japan those countries dominate on this region and effect on each other. In General, The Global competitiveness imposes restrictions on these countries and on Taiwan in particular, especially in view of China's current economic

dominance [50]. Second: Economic independency, the Strategic partnership helps to find alternatives to the Economic Independency and limits the great dependence on the Chinese economy. The numbers that the exchange trading between the two countries reaches make a number of Taiwan Citizens feel worry about that. The partnership considers one of the important chances to show the possibility of adoption the Taiwan Economy as independent country [51]. Third: Overcoming labor shortages, having the labor shortages problem will lead to higher cost of production of goods. The partnership with Jordan helps to solve the unemployment problem by exploiting the potential of Jordanian labor [52]. Fourth: Exploiting the featured international Jordanian relationships: Jordan has as strong relationships with other countries around the world and that will help to make a bigger agreement with other countries around the world. Fifth: Exploiting the security, political and economic corporation between Jordan and other countries and that will help to present the possibility to use the benefits of Jordan – Taiwan. The Jordanian relationship in the international field not limited to the regional level but also expands to the all corporation fields, for instance; Diversity experience in Jordan through the large participation in international peacekeeping missions makes Jordan attracts everyone's attention in addition to that helps to increase the possibility of take advantage of the corporation between Jordan – Taiwan, for example: provide cloths for the disaster areas and for the refugees. Sixth :uniqueness : the uniqueness of Taiwan in the Products , technological Potential, connections and food production quality and trust , especially the Seafood [53] and that thing makes Taiwan possible to present itself strongly in other countries through Jordan which can be exploited by the food company in Jordan so can provide food to the International peacekeeping missions, and its increasingly competitive as a result of diversity and multiplicity of options which can provide chances more acceptable than others. Seventh: contribution in the Humanitarian aspects: the Taiwanese ability in various aspects especially in recycling of clothes which supports in a good way to help the Syrian refugees in Jordan and in neighboring countries [54]. Eighth: Enhance the chances of success of Taiwan's economy. The partnership principle reduces the impacts of economic crises which were happened around the world, opens the Prospects to extend and invest in the Stricken countries especially in Middle East as Iraq and Syria, it can create more chances and a wider area to market various products and that will

help to open another companies [55], especially that the huge available expected productivity of Taiwan has the ability to respond rapidly for the market requirements and the required quantities on time, and that makes it stress on the other competitors from other countries. Ninth: provide researches and the useful scientific studies: Education in Taiwan is characterized by high level, and that can be an important reference to a lot of countries. the partnership with Taiwan can be the most important step to stop the Scientific decline in the university level especially, in the Arabic World; because Taiwan has a huge experience in helping to treat this defect through: The Applied Scientific Programs which aims to increase the students' knowledge and be unique in some of the scientific value for these applications as providing the electronic Software to ease the contact between the teaching, employees and students. Tenth: reducing the financial cost of products: the corporation between Jordan and Taiwan reduces the cost of transportations and taxes which affects positively on reducing the financial costs, and it can obtain it easily and rapidly within a short period of time, so the corporation products have a success chances. Eleventh: maintain companies and properties: the common interests between the two parties whether Taiwan or Jordan increased of the value benefits in each one to provide the best, especially this institute which has a final benefit for both. Jordan also can provide protection, all the incomes and suggestion, provide the raw materials which are necessary in manufacturing, so all of them will feel how is important to be with this institute and how much will gain advantages whether physical or intangible, so it is a step to know the facts which happen in the strategic environment and the effects of the taken decisions.

2.9 The benefits of the strategic partnership for Jordan

Few benefits are embossed throughout the partnership present by: First: supporting the national economy: Jordan is seeking to find different ways to improve the efficiency of the national economy's production. The partnership with Taiwan leads the Jordanian industry to arise in the center of the field with its high quality production that opens the gate front big number of them to emboss in the competition. Second: commitment and compliance: the commitment has great influence on the improvement and development of each part [56], whereas it builds trust and confidence for a long period of time at the regional and national level. Third: Fighting against the social conflicts: Jordan

suffers from some serious social problems that affects the society such as; corruption, bureaucracy, the obligations set for each part prevent and control the corruption, as result of the contentious controlling. Forth: increase the criteria of knowledge and education: Economy requires high standers of knowledge and competent environment to have that knowledge in order to equals the input data with the required results, as long as the process of doing so. This progress could assure gaining skills, embosses the role of the Institutions eligible for employment and professionalism at the regional and global levels [57]. Five: Reducing unemployment: the abilities of Jordan exploit to provide the employees from all the society classes. Six: improving the society: providing of the needed infrastructure as the high speed Trains will develop the feeling of belonging to these institutes of the state and will ease the local society responding to the state projects [58]. Seven: stopping the student Violence in Universities: The Violence problem in universities considered one of the most dangers evil happens in the Jordanian Privet universities campus as a result of not efficiency of the Educational System in terms of the educational requirements and the students' performance in the universities. We can treat this problem by applying the Taiwanese educational system which is unparalleled with other because their system leans on the advanced educational Curricula, also it includes a social activity for the students to increase the society caring of the National affiliation for the state. Eight: tourist development the Taiwanese experiences on the professional tourism are through providing services, infrastructure and the main requirements [59]. The adoption of the Taiwanese method in tourism makes the Jordanian tourism one of the most important primary sources for its economy because it creates many of the job opportunities chances. Ninth: services sector: the citizens look to the state value which is characterized of its ability to employ its abilities to serve the citizens. Taiwan considers one of the best examples of providing the services to its citizens. Making the services under a system sponsored by the state oblige its citizens to comply with laws as a result of the services provided to them. Ten: community service: the economical corporation between Jordan and Taiwan is not limited only to the companies but also to serve the community [60]. Jordan has a long period of experience in supporting the institutions of the state which have big sectors as the Veterans, The Military Institute for Retirees in addition to a various projects and experiences. So the corporation between Jordan and Taiwan in sustaining the big sectors in the local communities is possible.

2.10 Elements of the Strategy

2.10.1 Time and location

The projects related to the new economic policies requires a continuing success step by step, because any failure will break down the joint ventures for both parties, so it shall be done in stages and the first stage of the partnership includes some of the main products that are widely available and have high rate of success. For the second stage of the products expansion includes other areas of products or services and the third one, is starting of the projects in other countries such as production projects and services in the Arab countries.

2.10.2 Facilitates

All facilities which provided by the parties shall be comprehensive, whereas the companies which was founded depend on the base of partnership to achieve the intended results, and it shall include the facilities: First, financial facilities, all the financial aspects for goods, like tax exemption, and exploitation of industrial cities to take advantage of tax exemptions to export it to the United States. Second, reinforcement Prospects of success by gaining information about markets in Arab countries and giving the advice to them. Third, the required work for the submitted projects should be in lower costs. Fourth, some instructions need to modify the laws to reduce the social defects like the corruption and bad bureaucracy. Fifth, exploit of the available mass media to market the products. Sixth, work as a team and confer between the parties to avoid differences in opinions. Seventh, provide the protection and security for all institutions which belong to the partnership for both parties.

2.10.3 Joint Projects

The continuous of various joint economic projects between the two parties can achieve maximum possibilities between the two parties, which reflect and reinforce the image of each party in a positive way, a strong presence at the international level, contribute to open hopes and aspirations for each of them through the following projects:

- 1- Beginners companies on the principle of equal partnership for all parties in all economic cases.
- 2- University connectivity in education and reinforce the success opportunities.
- 3- Participation in international projects such as food companies and international organizations as the United Nations.

- 4- The tourism industry and the exchange of tourist groups between the two countries.
- 5- Social service projects, through the establishment of distinguished infrastructure services at stages in Jordan and develop it in the future to give other neighboring countries such as Egypt and Iraq.
- 6- Participation in development projects for small communities such as the Veterans, The Military Institute for Retirees.
- 7- Open Seafood projects and fishery.

3. CONCLUSION

The principle of partnership between Taiwan and Jordan is available complying with the efforts of both countries to develop. The advanced technology in Taiwan can be exploited in more than one area in Jordan. That needs to finish the accumulated experiences because the future between the two countries favorable especially at light of the many fields that could be exploited in Jordan. Moreover, it can be launched in the future to other countries, so Jordan can be a solid base for neighboring countries. The ability of Taiwanese society to build modern communities is clear; it can be used in the absence of the ability of others. The political stability, security, and trends of States toward democracy, freedom of thought, and the development gain Jordan and Taiwan the influential ability in other countries and local communities. Especially at light of the abilities of Jordan in international relations, it's a series extends to the most countries. Also the abilities of Taiwanese economic enormous has reached the global level. In addition to that, the two parties have the capacity to rehabilitate humans in modern scientific ways. The partnership strategy is applicable and to ensure its success it has to be applied to partial and multiple stages to ensure its success, because there are many of exchange economic fields between the two countries, the joint interest between the two countries are not limited on traditional economic aspects but also is divided into the depths of the search for substance and the value of respect for humanity and life development.

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